

www.arseam.com

LIFE SKILLS OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR GUIDANCE NEEDS

Arulselvi. V

Assistant Professor,
Department of Education (SDE),
Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, India

Abstract

Life skills help children navigate the challenges of everyday life. They enable them to develop into healthy, responsible, and productive member of the society. The life skills have been identified as a key resource for enhancing positive and dynamic development in the adolescents. Being an adolescent, they need authentic guidance to direct them towards informed decision in areas that have direct impact in their development. Keeping this fact in view, investigator aimed at assessing the relationship between life skills and guidance needs of adolescents studying in higher secondary schools so as to enhance students' achievement. Sample consists of 102 adolescents (27 males and 75 females) studying in classes IX and XI in Coimbatore by using simple random sampling method. A descriptive survey was adopted with the help of self-administered questionnaires to collect data regarding life skills and guidance needs. The results revealed that there was no significant difference found between male and female, nuclear and joint family in the life skills of adolescents whereas there existed significant difference between class IX and XI students. It is also observed that female adolescents, adolescents from nuclear family and standard XI students need high guidance need requirements in the Physical, Social, Psychological, Educational and Vocational areas. Relationship analysis shows that there exists significant positive correlation between life skills and guidance needs of adolescents which shows that when students develop their life skills in every stage of life, they require guidance needs as well. Hence, study reveals life skills achievement needs proper guidance in every stage of human being especially in adolescent which requires extra care to acquire life skills.

Key words: life skills, guidance needs, adolescents.

1. Introduction

Education is not an end, but a means to an end. The ultimate aim of education is to prepare students for their future life. Adolescents suffer from psychosocial problems during their developmental stage. Many of these problems are of transient nature and are often not noticed. It is known that there remains a significant gap between adolescents having accurate information and its translation into behaviour. Skill development is a key to facilitate this process of transforming information into healthy behaviour. Adolescents with low levels of life skills are known to develop high risk behaviours which lead to long lasting psychosocial problems. Many countries across the world have introduced life skills education in the school curriculum or for adolescents in special situations. Life skills are abilities for adaptive and positive behavior that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands, challenges, and stress of everyday life. Adolescence is the developmental period during which one acquires these skills through various methods. In considering the kind of assistance that a person needs, it is necessary to focus on the personality role problems along the dimension of intensity of the internal disturbance. These difficulties may stem from any psychic factor or from emotional difficulties requiring special learning. Life skills are a comprehensive set of universal cognitive and non-cognitive skills and abilities, connecting behavior, attitudes, and knowledge, which adolescence can develop and retain throughout their lives. Life skills increase ones well-being and help them to develop into active and productive members of their communities. WHO has defined life skills as “abilities for adaptive and positive behavior that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life,” while UNICEF has defined them as a *“large group of psychosocial and interpersonal skills that can help people make informed decisions, communicate effectively, and develop coping and self-management skills that may help lead a healthy and productive life.”* The basic life skills, which need to be taught at the schools level especially to adolescents, are as follows; cognitive skills, communication and assertive skills and social skill.

2. Significance

Life skills are needed to promote ones’ health and well-being. If adolescents developed with good health and well-being, problems raised in their development stage may reduce at minimum. The generic type of life skills such as decision-making, problem solving, creative

thinking, critical thinking, self-awareness, empathy, coping with emotions, coping with stress, interpersonal skills, communication skills, and self-care to be flourished among adolescents through training and experience. These skills must be evaluated periodically among adolescents to make them strong in developing life skills. However, they may need guidance in every stage even in the development of personality or in the failure of personality to cope with the demands of role performance. Guidance is the assistance given to individuals in making intelligent choices and adjustments. It is based on the conception that is the duty and the right of every individual to choose his/her own way of life as long as his / her choice does not interfere with or infringe on the rights of others. It is based on the belief that the ability to make such choices is not innate but like other abilities must be developed. Every individual is potentially capable of achieving his goals. But from childhood he is continuously hampered by internal barriers. He has to learn to overcome the internal obstacles and free his latent creative power. Practically, those children with less practice of life skills develop fewer friends; they tend to avoid activities, such as sports, drama, and debate that would put them in the limelight. Moreover, they tend to be perceived unfriendly, and untalented, and they tend to feel lonely and have low self-esteem (Jones & Carpenter, 1986). Children with low life skills tend to become anxious adults tend to have smaller social networks and to feel less satisfied than others with their social support networks. They need physical, psychological, social, emotional and vocational guidance needs to acquire appropriate life skills.

3. Objectives

In the light of the above reflections, the present study is planned with the objectives to find out;

- if adolescents' guidance needs and life skills achievement vary with respect to their gender, family type and class of study.
- To find out if there is any relationship between guidance needs and life skills achievement of adolescents.

4. Methodology

4.1 Design of the study

In order to assess the life skills and guidance needs of adolescents studying in higher secondary schools, a descriptive survey method is used to collect data from population. The two main variables of life skills as dependent variable and guidance needs as independent variable

are selected for the study. Gender, family type and class study are considered as sub-variables in the study.

4.2 Sample

Sample consists of 102 adolescent students (27 males and 75 females) studying in classes 9 and 11 in Coimbatore by using simple random sampling technique.

4.3 Tools used for the study

The life skill questionnaire is a self-reporting tool developed by Arpana and Lancy D'Souza (2012) which has 3 categories: Social skills had 6 statements; Assertiveness and Communication skills had 12 statements and Cognitive skills had 6 statements. The scores ranged from 1 to 5 according to Likerts' scale. Each item is scored as 5 for strongly agree, 4 for agree, 3 for uncertain, 2 for disagree or 1 for strongly disagree. Total score is computed by adding up the scores of each of the statements. The reliability of the scale was determined by split half (odd-even) method and Cronbach's alpha coefficient is found to be 0.82 and 0.84 respectively. Questionnaire has both face and content validity. Individual with high score is considered to have high levels of life skills.

Guidance Needs Inventory (GNI) was developed by Grewal, 1982 to identify the guidance needs of adolescent students. The GNI is to be filled by the students as his most pressing and least pressing needs. The GNI attempts to structure the need system of an individual student so that the degree to which the school or its guidance system provides satisfaction for each need type may be measured. The students has to express the needs on a 5 point scale through 5 possible answers given against each need items such as *Highly true, Mostly true, Quite true, Least true and Not true*. In the scoring of guidance needs, the increase in score indicates lower guidance needs and as the score goes down it indicates the higher need for guidance. The tools were administered to a sample of 102 adolescents (75 females and 27 males).

5. Hypotheses

1. There will be no significant difference in the life skills of adolescent students with respect to their;

- a. Gender
 - b. Family type
 - c. Class of study
2. There will be no significant difference in the guidance needs of adolescent students with respect to their;
 - a. Gender
 - b. Family type
 - c. Class of study
 3. There will be a significant relationship between guidance needs and life skills achievement of adolescent students.

6. Analysis of Data

For analyzing the data, students 't' test, was used to find out significant difference in life skills achievement and guidance needs with respect to their gender, family type and class of study. Pearson product moment correlation was used to find out the relationship between life skills achievement and guidance needs of adolescent students.

Table-1 t-Test shows the significant differences in the life skills of adolescents based on gender, family type and class of study

Variables	N	Mean	SD	't' Value
Male	27	91.85	11.93	0.81
Female	75	94.13	13.92	
Nuclear	89	93.71	10.74	0.20
Joint	13	92.23	25.78	
Standard IX	51	89.37	15.45	3.27
Standard XI	51	97.68	9.43	

Above analysis shows that there exist no significant difference between the mean scores of overall life skill achievement of adolescents with respect to their gender, family type and class of study. But, significant difference was found between adolescents studying in class IX and class XI. The overall life skills achievement is high for students studying in the class XI. Hence, hypothesis stated that there will be no significant difference in the life skills of adolescent students with respect to their gender, family type (1a & 1b) is accepted while hypothesis 1c is

rejected since there exist significant difference in the life skills of adolescent students with respect to their class of study.

Table-2 t-Test shows the significant differences in the guidance needs of adolescents based on gender, family type and class of study

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t Value
Male	27	149.29	60.95	4.31
Female	75	94.52	41.79	
Nuclear	89	104.97	52.26	2.02
Joint	13	136.69	52.26	
Standard IX	51	137.80	53.94	6.48
Standard XI	51	80.23	33.29	

Overall guidance needs is perceived as the total of the individual scores achieved in each of the 5 standardized components (physical, social, psychological, educational and vocational) of guidance needs. Table 2 shows that the overall guidance needs is found comparatively high among females, adolescents belonging to nuclear family and studying in class XI. t- value shows that there exists significant difference in the guidance needs with respect to gender, family types and class of study. Hence, hypothesis 2a,b,c (there will be no significant difference in the guidance needs of adolescent students with respect to their gender, family type and class of study) is rejected.

6.1 Correlation analysis

Variables	N	Mean	SD	'r' value
Life skills	102	93.52	13.40	0.6
Guidance needs		109.01	53.16	

Analysis shows that there exist significant positive correlation between life skills and guidance needs of adolescents which reveals that when student's life skills achievement increase their guidance needs (physical, social, psychological, educational and vocational) also increases. Hence, it is interpreted that sharpening of life skills with proper guidance would help in acquiring strength and confidence in life. Hence hypothesis 3 stated that 'There will be a

significant relationship between guidance needs and life skills achievement of adolescent students' is accepted.

7. Major findings of the study

- Life skills achievement is high among students studying in the standard XI.
- Significant difference was not found in the life skills between male and female, students belonging to nuclear and joint family.
- Guidance for physical, social, psychological, educational and vocational needs is found high among females, adolescents belonging to nuclear family and studying in class XI.
- Significant Positive relationship is observed between life skills and guidance needs (0.6) of adolescents.

8. Discussion

- The Life Skills acquisition is a comprehensive behavior change approach that concentrates on the development of the skills needed for life such as communication, decision-making, thinking, managing emotions, assertiveness, self-esteem building, resisting peer pressure, and relationship skills. Practice of life skill cum appropriate guidance services would help in empowering girls and guiding boys towards new values. As result revealed that Life skills achievement is high among students studying in the standard XI than IX students. It may be due to the fact that as age increases, students may find maturity in acquiring skills need for survival. As 't' test revealed, there was no significant difference found between male and female, students belonging to nuclear and joint family in life skills achievement. It is understood that gender and family type do not play any role in life skills achievement. So, it can be interpreted that life skills are important equally for both gender and families irrespective of their personal constraints.
- Guidance needs for physical, social, psychological, educational and vocational is found high among females, adolescents belonging to nuclear family and studying in class XI. It may be due to the fact that as females and adolescents belonging to nuclear family do have minimum exposure in all aspects of life, they ultimately need guidance for development. Since standard XI students acquired life skills in higher level, they also need guidance in all areas for their further improvement and sustenance of life skills.

- As positive relationship is observed between life skills and guidance needs of adolescents, life skills achievement increases in one's life, they may also require proper guidance for life orientation.

9. Implications of the study

The emotional bond of adolescents with their parents and teachers may help them get rid of psychological problems. According to psychologists, children who don't have attachment and appropriate guidance do not possess with adequate life skills. When guidance and counselling is inconsistent and unreliable, adolescents would not get feeling of security, affection, and comfort which result in shyness and some psycho social problems. Teachers should be provided with knowledge and skills to impart life skill education to the adolescents so as to enable them to deal with the adolescents having psychosocial problems. When teachers assess childrens' life skills and guidance needs in parallel, it will be convenient for school management to give appropriate life skills training cum guidance and counselling in which area they are suppressed with. The guidance counsellor would help children discover for himself some blocked path, the clearance of which enable them to move forward. Hence this study will be an eye opener for the stakeholder to work out the findings of this study so as to make the life skills training and guidance services one of the component in the school curriculum.

10. Conclusion

The personality of adolescents is moulded by various factors among which family and school are the most important. With the passage of time, there have been substantial changes in the family and school structure which has led to considerable changes in adolescent development. Due to the increasing rate of changes taking place in our society as a result to globalisation, it will be inadequate if guidance of adolescents is confined only to parents and elders. Professional guidance is the need of the hour to deal with the increasing problems of adolescents due to globalisation. Parental guidance along with healthy school environment when acted synergistically with professional guidance will have a profound positive impact on adolescent development and will enable them to become healthy and competent young adults.

References

1. World Health Organization (1997). Life Skills Education for Children and Adolescents in Schools. Introduction and Guidelines to Facilitate the Development and Implementation of Life Skills Programs. World Health Organization - Programme on Mental Health. Doc. WHO/MNF/PSF/93.7A.Rev.2. Geneva: World Health Organization, p. 1. 3
2. UNICEF (2012). Evaluation Report: Global Evaluation of Life Skills Education Programs, pp. vi, viii, 1, and 7.
3. Grewal JS 1982. Manual for Guidance Needs Inventory. Agra: National Psychological Corporation.
4. D'Souza, L., Gowda, H.M. R & Gowda, D.K.S. (2006). Relationship between shyness and fear among High school students. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 21, 3-4, 53-60.
5. Morris AM, Steinberg L 2001. Adolescent development. *Ann Rev of Psych*, 52: 83-110.